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РАЗРАБОТКА И ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ ПРИВОДНОГО МЕХАНИЗМА УСТРОЙСТВА ДЛЯ ДОЗИРОВАНИЯ ЖИДКИХ И СЫПУЧИХ МАТЕРИАЛОВ

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DEVELOPMENT AND RESEARCH OF THE DRIVE MECHANISM OF THE DEVICE FOR DOSING LIQUID AND BULK MATERIALS

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Аннотация

Статья посвящена разработке и исследования приводного механизма устройств для дозирования жидких и сыпучих материалов. Приведен анализ конструкции и принцип работы предлагаемого приводного механизма, разработанное нами на уровне патента. В статье также даны материалы теоретический исследований дозируемой нормы жидких и сыпучих материалов в зависимости от конструктивных параметрах и режимов работы приводного механизма установленными дозаторами жидких и сыпучих материалов.

Abstract

The article is devoted to the development and research of the drive mechanism of devices for dosing liquid and bulk materials. The analysis of the design and the principle of operation of the proposed drive mechanism, developed by us at the patent level, is given. The article also provides materials for theoretical studies of the dosage rate of liquid and bulk materials, depending on the design parameters and operating modes of the drive mechanism installed dispensers of liquid and bulk materials.

Ключевые слова: разработка, исследование, приводной механизм, устройство, дозирования, жидкость, сыпучий материал, порционный, непрерывный, ручной, автоматический.

Keywords: development, research, drive mechanism, device, dosing, liquid, bulk material, batch, continuous, manual, automatic.

The results of analytical studies show that one of the labor-intensive operations in the agricultural sector is the dosing of liquid and bulk materials during sowing, row-to-row processing of crops, etc. [1...10], which was the main task for scientists working in the field of development of similar technical means.

Despite the fact that there are a number of technical means and design developments in this area, but using them, the rate of application of liquid and bulk materials during sowing, row-to-row processing of crops in the cultivated area (along the course of the device) is distributed unevenly.

Taking into account these disadvantages, we have developed and investigated a drive mechanism with manual and automatic control:

A – installed in an automatically controlled device for continuous fluid supply;

B – installed in an automatically controlled device for the portion supply of liquid;

C - installed in a manually operated device for continuous feeding of bulk material;

D – installed in an automatically controlled device for batch feeding of bulk material.

- A. To implement the requirements:

- uniform distribution of liquid preparations along the movement of the device and ensuring the norm according to the requirements of agricultural machinery;

- increase in operational, technological, economic and environmental indicators of sprayers, we [11] have developed and manufactured new drive mechanism for the OPSH-15 sprayer for uniform distribution of chemicals along the course of the sprayer [12], the general view of which is given in Fig. 1 and its technological scheme is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig.1. General view of the drive mechanism to OPSH-15: 1 is sprayer tank; 2 is running wheel; 3,4 is sprocket; 5 is chain transmission; 6 is centrifugal regulator Watt; 7 is gate valve; 8 is valve stem.

Fig. 2. Technological diagram of the drive mechanism installed in an automatically controlled device for continuous fluid supply:

1-Watt centrifugal regulator; 2,3 are lever; 4 is load; 5 is chain; 6 is shaft of the centrifugal regulator; 7 is slider; 8 is U-shaped connecting part; 9 is bearing; 10 is gate; 11 is housing; 12 is spring; 13,14 is adjustable nuts; 15,16 is nut- screw pair; 17 is tank; 18 is pump; 19,20,21 is hose.

The construction of the drive mechanism and its principle of operation are given below. The drive mechanism installed in an automatically controlled device for continuous liquid supply contains a container 17 in which the liquid enters the inlet window of the valve body 11 using a pump 18 through a hose 19. The rotation of the shaft 6 of the centrifugal regulator 1 is carried out through a chain transmission 5 from the support-drive wheel of the unit (not shown). At different speeds of rotation of the shaft with the help of a spring 12, adjustable nuts 13,14 with weights 4 and levers 2,3, the slider 7 moves to different values along the shaft. Since the gate valve 10 is connected to the slider, with

the help of a bearing 9 and a U-shaped connecting part 8, when the slider rotates, the gate performs translational motion (Fig.2). The nut – screw pair 15,16 is designed to work with the device in a hospital, and the hoses 20, 21 are designed to send the liquid respectively back to the tank and the object being processed. The drive mechanism, which is installed in an automatically controlled device for continuous fluid supply, works as follows. When the sprayer moves (not shown), the rotation from its support – drive wheel is transmitted to the shaft of the centrifugal regulator 6 through a chain transmission 5. Also, the liquid from the tank 17 through the pump 18 through the hose 19 enters the

valve. When the speed of the sprayer changes, the frequency of rotation of the shaft of the centrifugal regulator also changes, with the help of levers 2,3, the loads 4 diverge, the slider 7 with the gate 10 moves along the shaft, therefore, the incoming fluid flow into the inlet window of the valve is distributed by a hose 20 into the tank, and by a hose 21 into the processed object. In order to transmit the translational movement of the gate a bearing 9 is rigidly mounted on the slider relative to the housing 11, during rotation of which the outer cage is unchanged. The initial position of the gate (scraper) 10 is adjusted using nuts 13, 14 (in the working position of the sprayer). To use this drive mechanism in a stationary position, that is, to regulate the distribution of fluid flows in a stationary position, the valve body is moved to the required value and its position is fixed using a nut-screw pair 15,16, depending on the speed of the sprayer, with the help of a spring 12, the slider returns to its original position. With the use of the proposed drive mechanism for adjusting the fluid rate, hydraulic shock is also eliminated. This is achieved as follows. The area of the entrance window is equal to the sum of the areas formed by the two outlet openings of the housing and the gate opening.

As can be seen from Fig. 3. (b), at different values, the movement of the gate relative to its body is preserved

$$S = S_1 + S_2$$

In this case, the distance between the horizontal axes of the two outlet openings of the housing and the gate opening is, respectively, from the following dependence:

$$A \geq 2C$$

$$B \geq 3S,$$

where C is the sides of the square (Fig. 3 (a)).

During the research were studied the following qualitative indicators of adaptation to the sprayer:

- the influence of different constructive parameters and operating modes of the drive mechanism;
- the influence of different constructive parameters and operating modes of the drive mechanism on the distribution of the working fluid along the device.

Analysis of studies have shown that when using the drive mechanism (at $V_{opr} = 1.67 \text{ m/s}$; $\omega_{(c.r)} = 30c^{-1}$), the spring elasticity –

$Z_{pruzh} = 16.7 \times [10]^{-3} \text{ n/m}$, the angle of the spray torch - $\alpha = [105]^\circ$ in the sprayer, the required norm of liquid along the path of movement along the width of the grip, distributed more evenly, relatively without it.

Fig. 3. Calculation scheme

-B. The technologies currently used for cultivating and harvesting crops in all zones are characterized by high labor costs, which is explained by the lack of machines for such labor-intensive operations as weed control. Mechanical, chemical, biological, agrotechnical, etc. are used to control weeds. methods. In irrigation melon cultivation, the chemical method is most effective. Its effectiveness largely depends on the method of application of pesticides [13; 14; 15; 16; 17].

To increase the technological possibility of the method of applying pesticides, we have developed a

drive mechanism (Fig.4) installed on a seeder converted for nesting sowing of melons.

The drive mechanism installed on the portion distributor of the liquid contains a cork distributor, a centrifugal regulator, the shaft of which is kinematically connected to the shaft of the sowing disc of the seeder with the use of a regulating coupling.

The drive mechanism works as follows. When the seeder moves, the rotation from the support-drive wheels 6 through the chain drive 7 is transmitted to the shaft 5 of the sowing disc 2 and the rotating plug 16 of the portion distributor. When the radial channels 22 of

the rotating plug are combined with the outlet window 18 of the distributor housing 17, the liquid from the tank 26 through the filter 27 by the pump 28 under pressure through the inlet window 20 of the lid 19 is injected into the cavity 21 of the plug through the tip 29 by strips 30 around the socket, and when combined with the additional window 25, the liquid flows back into the tank 26 through the hose 24 for mixing (hydraulic mixer) of the working solution.

With an increase in the speed of the unit, the rotation frequency (ω_{vd}) of the shaft 1 of the centrifugal regulator increases. With the help of levers 10, the loads 11 diverge, the slider 14 with the distributor body 17 moves along the shaft. Consequently, the length L_i of the radial channel 22 of the plug 16 inside the seed nest. As can be seen from Fig. 1, $L_i + l_i = \text{const}$ (l_i is the length of the output window 18 increases, which corresponds to the time of liquid dosing around radial channel 22 of the plug 16 inside the additional window 25

Fig.4. Diagram of the drive mechanism to the seeder for the nest method of applying herbicides during sowing: 1.5 is shaft; 2 is sowing disc; 3 is cell of the sowing disc; 4 is regulating clutch; 6 is support-drive wheels; 7 is chain drive; 8-14 is slider; 9 is nut; 10 is lever; 11 is loads; 12 is spring; 13 is bearing; 15 is support; 16 is rotating plug; 17 is fluid distributor housing; 18 is housing outlet window; 19 is housing cover; 20 is housing inlet window; 21 is tube cavity; 22 is radial tube channel; 23 is oil seal; 24 is hose; 25 is additional outlet window of the housing; 26 is tank; 27 is filter; 28 is pump; 29 is tip; 30 is sprayed strip in the soil; 31 is seeds.

When the rotational speed of the centrifugal regulator is reduced by means of a spring 12, the distributor housing returns to its original position. This means that with the use of the proposed drive mechanism, with an increase in the speed of the aggregate, the dosing time increases and the application rate is ensured. As can be seen from Fig. 4, this is done when performing output windows in a combined trapezoidal housing. To improve the technological capabilities of the drive mechanism (for operation at different speeds, application rate and operating modes), the length of the spring is regulated by a nut-screw pair 9.

Since the cells 3 of the sowing disc 2 are equal to the number of radial channels 22 of the plug 16, with one revolution of the sowing disc, the same number of seed nests and injections into the protective strip 30 is obtained. The symmetry of the injections relative to the seed nest 31 is achieved by using a regulating coupling 4, i.e. with the use of a coupling, the shaft 5 of the sowing disc 2 is rotated relative to the shaft 1 of the plug 16. To prevent rotation of the distributor housing and fluid leakage, it is equipped with a support 15 and an oil seal 23.

The values of the design parameters of the cork fluid distributor are derived from the following expressions:

Since the cells 3 of the sowing disc 2 are equal to the number of radial channels 22 of the plug 16, with

one revolution of the sowing disc, the same number of seed nests and injections into the protective strip 30 is obtained. The symmetry of the injections relative to the seed nest 31 is achieved by using a regulating coupling 4, i.e. with the use of a coupling, the shaft 5 of the sowing disc 2 is rotated relative to the shaft 1 of the plug 16. To prevent rotation of the distributor housing and fluid leakage, it is equipped with a support 15 and an oil seal 23.

The values of the constructive parameters of the work fluid distributor are derived from the following expressions:

$$\beta_C = \arccos \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{C}{R} \right)^2 \right]; \beta_E = \arccos \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{E}{R} \right)^2 \right];$$

$$\beta_K = \arccos \left[1 - \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{K}{R} \right)^2 \right]; E \leq \frac{A \sin \alpha - H \cos \alpha + 2r}{\sin \alpha};$$

$$K \leq \frac{(A+E) \sin \alpha - H \cos \alpha + 2r}{\sin \alpha}; C \leq \frac{2r}{\sin \alpha}$$

where C, E, K are the chords of the central angles $\beta_C, \beta_E, \beta_K$

R is the radius of the traffic jam;

A is the length of the larger base of the trapezoid;

H is the height of the trapezoid;

α is the angle between the base and the side

trapezoids;

r is the radius of the radial channel of the plug [13].

When operating the developed drive mechanism with the given design parameters, the hydraulic shock of the liquid is prevented by the batch method of its supply.

The device ensures the reliability of the technological process. Optimal parameters: the height of the tip installation from the soil is 0.12 m; the angle of the spray torch is 1.83 rad, the studied pressure in the system is 0.15...0.35 MPa; the speed of the unit is 0.9...1.95 m/s; the number of radial channels of the plug is 7; the rotation frequency of the plug is 0.81...2.0 s⁻¹; the radius of the plug is 0.03 m; the radius of the radial channels of the plug is 0.0025 m; the length and width of the insertion strip is -0.3 m; the distance between the centers of the insertion strip is -1 m.

The economic effect of the application of the drive mechanism to the seeder for the nesting application of herbicides when sowing melons is 8000 dollars. US\$ per car.

C. The general view of the drive mechanism installed in the dispenser of bulk materials [5] is shown in Fig. 5. The drive mechanism contains an auger, the coils 1 of which are made of elastic material, the dispenser case 2, made with outlet openings 3, shaft 4, auger, the free end of the hinge is connected to the housing 5, the hopper of bulk material, the other horses

Fig. 5. Manual drive mechanism installed in the dispenser of bulk materials

D. Taking into account the relevance of the uniform distribution of bulk material over the treated area during the batch method of application, we have developed a drive mechanism [3], the general view of which is shown in Fig.6.

The drive mechanism contains a rack 1, a rack gear 2, a bevel gear pair 3,4, a drive shaft 5, a regulating clutch 6, a screw coil 7 made of elastic material, the free end of which can be moved along the shaft 8. The rotation of which is carried out through a gear pair 9,10, the ends of the shaft 8, pivotally connected to a movable support 11,12. The drive of the bulk material dispenser is transmitted from the Watt centrifugal regulator. The centrifugal regulator contains a non-movable 13 and a movable 14 element, springs 15. The fixed and movable element, respectively, are connected by hinges 16,17 and 18,19 with a lever 20,21; 22,23 and weights 24,25. Adjustment of the spring length is carried out by a nut 26.

For undesirable movement of the movable element of the Watt regulator, nuts 27 are used, the end

the screw shaft with the help of a washer 6 has a rigid connection with the screw screw, and the other end of the screw with the help of a nut – screw pair 7 has the ability to move along the shaft to change the angle α_i [$\alpha_i = f(A)$] of the screw turn.

Manual adjustment of the angle of the screw (which is associated with the norm of bulk material) in the dispenser of bulk materials, a friction reducer is used, the horizontal disk 8 of which has a rigid shaft connection connected to the support wheel 9 through a bevel gear reducer. The movement of the free end of the screw turn together with the washer 6 is moved along the shaft using a screw pair of a manual handle 10.

When installed in the bulk material dispenser, the drive mechanism works as follows: when the bulk material dispenser moves, the rotation from the supporting drive wheels 9 is transmitted to the horizontal discs 8 of the friction reducer, kinematically connected to the vertical discs, which, with movement relative to along the screw shaft, changes the angle of the screw of the dispenser, with a change, which also changes the portion rate of the bulk material. The application of which the bulk material in the treated area is distributed evenly, by changing the angle of the screw turn depending on the speed of movement of the dispenser

of the spring 7 are pivotally and rigidly connected, respectively, by U-shaped elements 28 and 29. When the screw rotates, the bulk material 30 moves in the direction of the outlet window 31, made by the dispenser housing 32. With fixed elements 33, the hopper has a rigid connection.

The drive mechanism works as follows: in contrast to the principle of operation of the drive mechanism installed in an automatically controlled device for batch feeding of bulk material from the drive mechanism installed in a manually controlled device for continuous feeding of bulk material is that it is not operated indoors. It can be seen that with a slight change in design, it can be used in agriculture for the introduction of bulk materials. The difference in the principle of operation is that the regulation of the nesting rate of bulk material is carried out automatically, that is, depending on the speed (v_{ag}) of the movement of the unit (dispenser) during operation in the field (or the angular velocity [ω]₂ when using the dispenser indoors).

To determine the flow rate of bulk material for different design parameters and operating modes of the dispenser, we have given below the following analytical study.

First we define a_i (connected A)

$$\alpha_i = \varphi(K_1; K_2; F), \quad (1)$$

where K_1 , K_2 are the stiffness of the regulator spring, respectively, Watt and the screw turns of the dispenser.

F is the centrifugal force.

It is known from physics that $F = m\omega^2 r$, (2)

m is the mass of the loads of the Watt regulator;

ω is the frequency of rotation of the shaft of the Watt regulator;

r is movement of the center of the load from the axis of symmetry of the shaft of the Watt regulator;

$$[\omega]_2 = f(v_{ag}) \quad (3)$$

v_{ag} is the speed of movement of the unit.

It can be seen that $A = \beta(\alpha)$ (4)

Given (3) in (2) we get $F = m[f(v_{ag})]^2 r$ (5)

Also considering (5) in (4) we get:

$$\alpha_i = \varphi\{K_1; K_2; m[f(v_{ag})]^2 r\}. \quad (6)$$

To determine the norm of the portion of bulk material, we first determine A , depending on the design parameters and operating modes of the dispenser, we get:

$$A = \beta \langle \varphi\{K_1; K_2; m[f(v_{ag})]^2 r\} \rangle \quad (7)$$

It is known that

$$[Q]_{shnek} = n(A; D_{shnek}), \quad (8)$$

Given (7) in expressions (8) we get:

$$[Q]_{shnek} = n \langle \beta \varphi\{K_1; K_2; m[f(v_{ag})]^2 r\}; D_{shnek} \rangle \quad (9)$$

Fig.6. Automatic drive mechanism installed in the dispenser of bulk materials

The relevance of the proposed drive mechanism is the simplicity of design and operation, that is, a large technological, economic and environmental opportunity gives its use in addition to the agricultural sector, also in the development of technical means in the heavy, light and food industries.

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